

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF USING CLIL TECHNOLOGY IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

A.Amirkulov

Teacher: MK Academy

e-mail: asliddinamirkulov905@gmail.com

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Abstract: This article discusses the theoretical foundations of using CLIL technology in the educational process. The CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) technology allows for a comprehensive study of both English language and the content being learned. Such technologies enhance the learner's interest, as well as their enthusiasm for acquiring and learning new information. Based on the CLIL teaching technology, students develop communicative competencies in an expanded and integrated manner. It implements dual objectives of mastering the planned topic simultaneously in both English and the native language.

Keywords: competence, culture, efficiency, integration, information, quality, technology

Today, the introduction of advanced and tested methods from around the world into the national education system is yielding positive results in acquiring modern knowledge, skills, and competencies. Regardless of the method or approach used to deliver modern knowledge to students, it must serve to elevate both quality and outcomes to a higher level. One such effective mechanism is CLIL technology.

CLIL technology is a mechanism for implementing bilingualism, providing students the opportunity to learn a foreign language alongside their native language. The term **CLIL** is an acronym derived from the English words: *Content* (meaning "subject," "field," or "topic"), *Language, Integrated* (meaning "integration" or "connection"), and *Learning*. CLIL technology recommends studying a new subject, field, or science in a foreign language, i.e., in a language other than one's native tongue.

In our country, the methodology for teaching languages has been studied by researchers such as Zh.Zh. Jalolov, L.T. Akhmedova, and others. In recent years, clear directions have emerged in the development and radical transformation of education both globally and in Uzbekistan. These include the democratization of education, the idea of lifelong learning (shifting from "education for life" to "education throughout life"), the role of education not only in preparing specialists but also in producing conscious and dedicated citizens for society, the

globalization of education, and informatization of the educational system, among others. Innovative approaches in education are accompanied by the integration of science, technology, and production, and the rapid growth of national development. Accordingly, the tasks of developing innovative educational programs are also becoming more prominent.

The use of CLIL technology in the process of learning English is considered a targeted approach that helps to develop bilingual competencies in students. CLIL technologies, based on various socio-linguistic, economic, and political contexts, assist in the integration of professional education levels and the development of initiative in students. Based on CLIL technology, both the English language and the content being studied can be thoroughly learned. These technologies stimulate students' interests and increase their enthusiasm for learning and gaining knowledge. With this approach, students can integrate English into their daily life through activities such as reading fairy tales, stories, watching films, listening to music, and other daily tasks. In other words, reading a small text in a foreign language can initiate a student's engagement with a full-length literary or informational work, which enhances their ability to learn a foreign language.

Through this, students will acquire knowledge in new subjects, particularly in fields such as mathematics, nature, literature, and others. Furthermore, skills related to searching for new information, creating, reading, listening, hearing, and understanding will be developed. The integration of one subject with another not only improves the quality of the educational process but also increases the efficiency of both teachers and students, helping to solve the most important tasks of education. Interdisciplinary connections facilitate the development of students' information literacy. Often, there are integration links between various fields, such as "Computer Science and English," "History and English," "Economics and English," and more. Integration can also be seen between disciplines like "Physics and Astronomy," "Biology and Ecology," "Physics and Mathematics," and "History and Social Sciences."

Under CLIL, the student develops expanded and integrated communicative competence in the subject area. The aim of CLIL is to allow students to master the content in both their native and foreign languages simultaneously, thus achieving dual objectives. The goal of CLIL technology is not only to help students become active members of society but also to provide them with the opportunity to study subject-specific terminology and concepts in English. Additionally, recent models in content-based language teaching emphasize the

link between learning a language and mastering a subject, serving as a foundation for understanding and integrating new concepts and meanings. The deep study of a topic cannot be carried out without considering its linguistic aspect. Of course, such technologies cannot completely replace learning a subject in a foreign language rather than in one's native language, but they can serve as a basis for significant positive changes in language learning. In modern, rapidly developing societies, there are serious processes of education modernization, which necessitate the improvement of teachers' qualifications. This, in turn, requires a new approach to education.

The use of CLIL technology in English language lessons is closely related to pedagogical technology, and the concept of "pedagogical technology" is used in three interconnected levels: general didactic, subject-specific, and modular education. Based on these levels, the use of CLIL technology in the educational process plays a significant role in the development of students as individuals in today's globalized world. Through CLIL technologies, in the process of developing students' bilingual competencies in English lessons, students will also develop universal human values, skills for analyzing the environment and society, confidence in competing, respect for different cultures and traditions, creativity, inventiveness, and self-confidence in problematic situations.

For this reason, our country's education system has been placing special emphasis on teaching both Western and Eastern languages.

In developed countries, where this process is well-understood, the integration of foreign languages with other subjects through the use of the CLIL methodology has shown positive results.

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